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Method for traceable calibration of 5G NR measuring receivers

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ABSTRACT

In the framework of metrology for the new emerging wireless standards such 5G New Radio (NR), the traceable calibration of 5G NR measuring receivers is presented in this contribution. A reference setup to measure the power of cell-specific synchronization resource elements in downlink 5G New Radio (NR) signals is introduced, providing the traceability of the measurements to the International System of Units (SI). This setup can be used to calibrate 5G code-selective measuring receivers that are utilized for the measurements of the radiation from base stations for mobile communication. This setup can also be used to calibrate not only the 5G signal receivers, but also the 5G generators. The method relies on the traceable measurements of the downlink signal generator by using an oscilloscope. It employs offline digital signal processing (DSP) demodulation algorithms that account for digital down-conversion, timing synchronization, frequency synchronization, phase synchronization, and robust 5G cell identification to generate the downlink time-frequency 5G grid. The applicability of this methods for both sub 6 GHz and millimeter wave frequency ranges are proven with experiments. Experimental results from conducted test scenarios demonstrate calibration capabilities with typical uncertainties of 0.05 dB ($k=2$). Moreover, the application of this method for the calibration of two commercial product and also the RF exposure assessment considerations are also explained in detail.

I. INTRODUCTION

The demand for high-speed mobile communication continues to grow due to increased usage of online content particularly on handheld devices, which is mainly driven by social media, high resolution videos and streaming. According to [1], the usage of mobile data has reached 201 exabytes (201 million terabytes) per month as of 2025. Moreover, 5G has accounted for around 34% of mobile data traffic by the end of 2024 and will carry 80% of mobile data traffic globally in 2030 [1]. 5G New Radio (NR) technology addresses this growing demand by providing larger bandwidth, better latency and enhanced adaptability not only through adapted modulation techniques, but also by employing smart antennas. However, this increase in data communication raises concerns about the overexposure to non-ionizing radiation emitted by base stations. The paradigm shift introduced by beam-steering technology with adaptive antennas and the possible increase of momentary exposure are currently being exhaustively investigated in order to ensure that, despite the enormous increase in amount of data transmitted every moment, public health remains uncompromised. These investigations focus on controlling legal exposure limits while traffic is transmitted using higher bandwidth and more focused beams. Current research indicates that exposure levels from 5G infrastructures are similar to those from existing mobile networks, with no adverse health effects causally linked to wireless technologies [2]. Studies by the FDA and FCC support the conclusion that RF exposure from mobile networks, including 5G, remains within safe limits and does not pose significant health risks [2], as long as the exposure limits are satisfied.

International RF safety standards play a crucial role in ensuring the safe deployment of 5G technology. The International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) has established guidelines to limit RF exposure and protect public health. The ICNIRP guidelines cover a wide range of frequencies from 100 kHz to 300 GHz, including those used in 5G technologies [2]. These guidelines are based on the best available scientific evidence and are periodically updated to reflect new research findings [2]. The guidelines specify quantitative limits

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2
3 for RF exposure to ensure safety for both the general public and occupational settings [2]. Compliance with ICNIRP
4 guidelines ensures that 5G technology can be safely integrated into our daily lives while delivering enhanced
5 communication capabilities. Most countries adopted ICNIRP guidelines for the national limits, for example
6 European countries as given in [3], US as given in [4], China as given in [5] and Switzerland as given in [6].
7

8 The compliance of the emission limits from the base stations can be verified with measurements by using appropriate
9 equipment. This equipment includes antennas or field probes together with appropriate cabling. These components
10 are connected to the measuring receivers. To ensure traceability, the equipment including the measurement receivers
11 need to be calibrated as required by Swiss regulation [6]. For 5G, the measurements can be made frequency selective
12 or code-selective [7]. The frequency selective methods are well-established and can be applicable also for this digital
13 communication technology. On the other hand, the code-selective measurements are recognized to be more
14 appropriate for determination of the exposure. The particularity of the code-selective measurements is that the cell
15 specific signals such as PSS or SSS for 5G [8] must be properly decoded and quantified. There are different commercial
16 devices able to provide RF exposure measurements based on the field strength of specific signals. For these specific
17 measurements, the SI traceability must be provided as well in order to provide the confidence that limits are not
18 violated and public health is not compromised.
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21 In a previous study [9], the full study of the SI traceable calibration of 4G LTE receivers was presented. This study
22 aims to support the application of metrology also for the 5G exposure measurements. With respect to LTE, NR is
23 more modular and numerous configurations are possible regarding the bandwidth usage, cell search, numerologies,
24 etc. [8]. The traceable measurements of 5G measuring receivers need to incorporate this modularity. Moreover, in
25 contrast to the 4G LTE code-selective measurements, the reference signals used for 4G [9] are not available in 5G,
26 where secondary synchronization signal (SSS) are needed [7]. For the measurements of the field strength associated
27 with this reference signal, the SI traceability must be provided. The SSS is selected for the decoding in this method
28 because its transmission power is independent of the traffic load and it is emitted periodically, typically every 20 ms,
29 making it particularly suitable for exposure assessments from base stations. This periodic and traffic-independent
30 nature allows for consistent and reproducible measurements, which are essential for traceable metrology
31 applications. The stable SSS measurements can then be used, not to measure the actual radiated power, but to
32 extrapolate to the maximum radiated power as requested from several regulations. The research presented in this
33 publication covers all these aspects.
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35

36 Accordingly, this contribution presents a complete work for traceable measurements of 5G power downlink
37 transmissions, from the conceptual considerations to the hardware and software implementations and the
38 experimental verification and the calibration of commercial products including the uncertainty of the measurement
39 method. Section II explains the details on the measurement principles, including the important basics of 5G standard,
40 the modular parameters to account for and the resource grid structure. The measurement setup based on a digital
41 oscilloscope with the required RF front end and the software module for the mathematical calculations for the
42 decoding algorithm are given in Section III. The experimental validation with measurement uncertainty calculations,
43 the corresponding budget and the results of the calibrations of two commercial 5G measuring receivers are given
44 Section IV. The application of such measurement results in the non-ionizing radiation RF exposure considerations
45 are illustrated in Section V. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in section VI.
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47

48 II. MEASUREMENT PRINCIPLE

49 For code-selective measurements, repetitive, stable and traffic-independent signals are needed [7]. Primary
50 synchronization signal (PSS), secondary synchronization signal (SSS) and physical broadcast channel demodulation
51 reference signals (PBCH DMRS) can constitute the best candidates. The above-mentioned control channels are
52 distributed over the complex 5G NR time-frequency grid as shown in Fig. 1. They are transmitted in Synchronization
53 Symbol Blocks (SSB) together with traffic (see Fig. 1). As defined by the regulators and studied many times in
54 different publications such as in [7], [10], [11] and [12], SSS is chosen to be the reference signals to measure in order
55 to assess the RF exposure from 5G base stations. Accordingly, many measuring receivers, which have the code-
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selective electromagnetic field (EMF) measurement capability for 5G downlink signals, measure the field strength of an individual resource element (RE) of SSS, and they provide one value representing the average of them. The SI traceability of these measurements can only be established when these signals can be directly calibrated.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the 5G NR downlink resource grid. The horizontal axis is the time axis sub-divided into blocks of OFDM symbols and the vertical axis is the frequency grid of OFDM subcarriers. Each block in the Time-Frequency grid is known as resource element and a group of 12 resource elements is called as a resource block. The SSS, PSS and PBCH signals are represented in green, light blue and orange respectively. They constitute together the synchronization symbol block (SSB) [8]. The traffic resource elements (dark blue) can be allocated very flexibly in both time and frequency in the whole resource grid.

A resource element of the Time-Frequency grid (RE) represents a fundamental information unit, whose "surface" is measured in Hz·s. A resource block (RB) consists of 12 simultaneous REs (aligned on the time axis, and adjacent in the frequency axis) and is used to organize different information blocks. In orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM), subcarriers transmit information and are spaced apart by a specific distance known as subcarrier spacing (SCS) along the available bandwidth. Fig. 2 summarizes the structure of RE and RB in both time and frequency domains. 5G transmissions can have a bandwidth from 10 MHz to 100 MHz for sub 6 GHz range, and up to 400 MHz for millimeter wave range.

Unlike LTE, which has a single subcarrier spacing of 15 kHz [13], 5G supports multiple OFDM subcarrier spacings Δf (or numerologies μ) as given in Table 1 [15]. Depending on the numerology, the lengths of subframes, slots and OFDM symbols change [15]. The visualization of these changes is given in Fig. 3 for numerologies 0, 1 and 2. The decoding algorithm needs to pay attention to this configurability in order to cover all possible schemes.

In time domain, the OFDM symbols in 5G transmission are grouped together to build structures. Downlink and uplink transmissions are organized into radio frames whose duration is 10 ms [15]. Each frame is divided into 10 subframes [15] and each subframe contains $N_{slot}^{subframe \mu}$ slots per subframe, which is a number dependent on the numerology [15]. Then each slot contains N_{symp}^{slot} symbols, which is 14 for normal prefix scheme and 12 for extended prefix scheme [15]. Table 1 summarizes this information.

For the decoding of 5G downlink transmissions, SSB structure must be known. SSB consists of 240 REs and it extends on 4 OFDM symbols [15]. SSBs include PSS, SSS and PBCH (See Fig. 4). In a single radio frame, there

could be more than one SSB burst depending on the configuration [15]. For frequencies lower than 3 GHz, there could be up to 4 SSB bursts, whereas for frequencies up to 6 GHz, there could be 8 SSB bursts [15]. Also, the starting of SSB burst in time domain is also dependent on the configuration [15]. Table 2 gives the details on OFDM starting symbols of candidate SSB and the number of possible SSBs depending on carrier frequency f_c .

Fig. 2. A resource element (RE) is the basic unit (Hz·s) in the resource grid, where the information is carried with a single subcarrier. A resource block (RB) constitutes of 12 REs and it is used to define different blocks of information. In orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM), the subcarriers carry the information and they lay with a certain spacing from each other, which is called subcarrier spacing (SCS). 5G resource grid allocation is very flexible in comparison with LTE. In LTE, SCS is defined as 15 kHz [13] whereas in NR, it can be $15 \cdot 2^\mu$ kHz where μ is an integer from 0 to 6 and denoted as numerology [8]. Every network can have a different SCS and even a combination of them. To provide network coverage, the numerologies used by different bands are defined by the standards [14].

Numerology μ	Subcarrier spacing/kHz $\Delta f = 2^\mu \cdot 15 \text{ kHz}$	Number of OFDM symbols per slot $N_{\text{ymb}}^{\text{slot}}$	Number of slots per subframe $N_{\text{slot}}^{\text{subframe } \mu}$	Number of slots per frame $N_{\text{slot}}^{\text{frame } \mu}$
0	15	14	1	10
1	30	14	2	20
2	60	14	4	40
3	120	14	8	80
4	240	14	16	160
5	480	14	32	320
6	960	14	64	640

Table 1. Possible configurations of numerologies, subcarrier spacings, number of OFDM symbols per slot $N_{\text{ymb}}^{\text{slot}}$, number of slots per subframe $N_{\text{slot}}^{\text{subframe } \mu}$ and number of slots per radio frame $N_{\text{slot}}^{\text{frame } \mu}$ in 5G NR transmissions [15]

Subcarrier Spacing	OFDM starting symbols of candidate SSB	$f_c \leq 3$ GHz ($L_{\max} = 4$)	3 GHz $< f_c \leq 6$ GHz ($L_{\max} = 8$)	6 GHz $\leq f_c$
Case A: 15 kHz ($\mu = 0$)	$\{2,8\} + 14n$	$n = 0,1$ $\{2,8,16,22\}$	$n = 0, 1, 2, 3$ $\{2,8,16,22,30,36,44,50\}$	Not used
Case B: 30 kHz ($\mu = 1$)	$\{4,8,16,20\} + 28n$	$n = 0$ $\{4,8,16,20\}$	$n = 0, 1$ $\{4,8,16,20,32,36,44,48\}$	Not used
Case C: 30 kHz ($\mu = 1$)	$\{2,8\} + 14n$	$n = 0,1$ $\{2,8,16,22\}$	$n = 0, 1, 2, 3$ $\{2,8,16,22,30,36,44,50\}$	Not used
Case D: 120 kHz ($\mu = 3$)	$\{4,8,16,20\} + 28n$	Not used	Not used	$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8,$ $10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 17, 18$
Case E: 240 kHz ($\mu = 4$)	$\{8,12,16,20,32,36,40,44\} + 56n$	Not used	Not used	$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8$
Case F: 480 kHz ($\mu = 5$)	$\{2,9\} + 14n$	Not used	Not used	$n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 31$

Table 2. Starting OFDM symbol index for all cases A to F and the number of possible SSBs during synchronization [8]. n is the repetition periodicity in symbols

Fig. 3. Radio frame, subframe and slots are configurable in 5G according to the numerology μ . In this figure, 3 examples are shown for numerology values of 0, 1 and 2. The slot and the subframe times are decreasing with increasing numerology number. The decoding scheme takes into account these changes according to the given numerology [15].

Fig. 4. Graphical representation for synchronization symbol block (SSB). Similar to all mobile networks, the base station transmits synchronization signals for the cell search, enabling the connection with the network, denoted as control channel. In the main control channel, three signals are transmitted: primary synchronization signal (PSS), secondary synchronization signal (SSS) and physical broadcast channel (PBCH). These signals lay all in an SSB and SSB bursts are emitted with a periodicity which is defined by a higher layer parameter taking values from the following list: {5ms, 10ms, 20ms, 40ms, 80ms, 160ms} [8].

III. 5G NR MEASUREMENT SET-UP

Using the synchronization signals, such as PSS, SSS or PBCH-DMRS, the traceability of 5G measurements can be achieved and the precision of 5G measuring receivers can be evaluated. PSS is present in the downlink resource grid with a periodicity given by the network and emitted by the base station at a predefined power when no power locking is applied [8]. In order to establish the fundamental capability for calibrating 5G measuring receivers, which deliver 5G EMF values for SSS signals, the setup is adjusted to calculate the power of SSS symbols.

The 5G measurement setup consists of a hardware and a software module. In the following subsections, these modules are explained in detail.

Hardware

To retrieve 5G resource grid in a traceable way, it is crucial to obtain a physical setup, which can be calibrated using standards derived from SI units. To extract and the measure the power of synchronization signals present in the resource grid, a laboratory hardware system has been assembled in order to calibrate the signal of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG) capable to simulate 5G signals. The 5G signal from the generator is typically modulated at a selected carrier frequency either in FR1 or FR2-1, with a bandwidth ranging from 10 MHz to 50 MHz. The signal is sent to a calibrated 6-dB power splitter, one output of which is connected to a power meter to measure the instantaneous RMS power of the incoming signal. The other output of the power splitter is input to the RF mixer. This signal is down-converted to obtain the signal at an Intermediate Frequency (IF) of 45 MHz (see Fig. 5). This down conversion is necessary to obtain a signal at a lower carrier frequency, which allows for more accurate digitization (in terms of the number of digitization bits) and less noise compared to digitizing the original signal. The down conversion is achieved by mixing the 5G signal with a sine wave from a local oscillator, and then filtering out the higher frequencies (see Fig. 5). The down-converted signal is then sampled and recorded by a digital oscilloscope. To ensure the setup is traceable and calibrated, the frequency response of the experimental setup is determined using a continuous wave (CW) signal, as the metrology of CW signals is well established. Correction factors can be applied to the digitized data to compensate for the non-linearity and the broadband characteristics of

the mixer and of the calibration chain, including the oscilloscope. The samples collected by the oscilloscope is then stored as a digital recording of the signal. This digital recording is then analyzed in terms of a post processing software.

Fig. 5. Experimental setup for 5G power measurements using oscilloscope-based measurement method

Post-processing Software

The extraction of SSS signals is accomplished purely by mathematical signal analysis. For this purpose, the recorded signal is treated as follows: I and Q signals (in-phase and quadrature components from the digitized 5G signal referred as I and Q respectively) are extracted by multiplying the input 45 MHz IF signal with $\cos(2\pi f_{IF} \cdot t)$ and $\sin(2\pi f_{IF} \cdot t)$, where f_{IF} is the intermediate frequency of 45 MHz, which is also known as digital-down conversion [16]. This complex baseband signal is digitally filtered in order to avoid the interaction of higher harmonics generated during the extraction of I and Q signals.

Next, the following steps listed below are conducted to process the 5G signal:

- Resampling the signal
- Timing synchronization of the signal (i.e., defining timing reference of the 5G grid structure)
- Extraction of the 5G symbols in time-domain (i.e., removing the cyclic prefix)
- Calculating the 5G symbols in the frequency domain (also called resource elements)
- Applying phase and frequency correction to the resource elements
- Determining the position of the SSS resource elements within the 5G grid
- Evaluating the mean power of the SSS resource elements within the 5G grid and computing the standard deviation of these values to get information on the quality of the power measurement.

5G employs numerous different configurations and the applications of the above-mentioned steps are not all trivial. Moreover, it is not required to perform the decoding of 5G signals in real-time. Hence, the above-mentioned post-processing algorithm has been chosen to preserve the full integrity of the resource elements. The most important steps of the above list are explained precisely in the following subsections.

Resampling Input Signal

As 5G NR is rather flexible for the employed subcarrier spacing defined by the numerology μ , where $\mu = 0, 1, \dots, 6$, the input signal must be resampled according to the basic time unit for the applied numerology.

The basic time unit for NR is

$$T_c = \frac{1}{(480 \text{ kHz}) \cdot 4096} \cong 0.509 \text{ ns} \quad (1)$$

where T_c corresponds to the sampling time for a subcarrier spacing of 480 kHz and a Fourier length of 4096.

The applied NR sampling time T_s is

$$T_s = \kappa \cdot T_C \text{ sec} \quad (2)$$

where $\kappa = 32$ for numerology 0 and $\kappa = 16$ for numerologies 1 and 2 as defined in the ETSI standard for NR systems [15].

Timing synchronization

After resampling the I and Q signals, timing synchronization is performed. This process is commonly referred to as cell search. There are no any precisely defined methods to obtain timing synchronization by the standards. Different synchronization techniques have been suggested in [17, 18, 19] using PSS present in the signal, which is applicable both for LTE and NR [9].

Like SSS, PSS is a frequency domain based BPSK maximum length sequences (known as M-sequences). M-sequences were selected because of not having time offset – frequency offset ambiguity which is present in Zadoff-Chu sequences employed in LTE [20].

M-sequence is a pseudorandom binary sequence. It can be created by cycling through every possible state of a shift register of length n . This results in a sequence of length 2^{n-1} . Both PSS and SSS are of length 127 [15].

The sequence $d_{PSS}(n)$ for the primary synchronization signal is defined by

$$d_{PSS}(n) = 1 - 2 \cdot x(m) \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} m &= (n + 43 \cdot N_{ID}^{(2)}) \bmod 127 \\ 0 &\leq n \leq 127 \\ N_{ID}^{(2)} &\in \{0, 1, 2\} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

and

$$x(i + 7) = (x(i + 4) + x(i)) \bmod 2 \quad (5)$$

The initial condition to generate all possible $d_{PSS}(n)$ is:

$$[x(6) \ x(5) \ x(4) \ x(3) \ x(2) \ x(1) \ x(0)] = [1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1 \ 0] \quad (6)$$

The presence and the position of PSS in the resource grid are obtained by correlating the recorded I and Q signals with those a priori known signals [21]. This method is implemented to obtain the timing synchronization. The M-sequence $d_{PSS}(n)$ as defined by ETSI [15] for PSS can be written as D_f^u for $0 \leq f \leq 126$. This represents the M-sequence in the frequency domain centered at the carrier frequency. To obtain this sequence in time-domain, its Fourier transform has to be calculated in the following way:

$$D^u(t_i) = \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^{63} d_{PSS_{j-1}} \cdot e^{\frac{-2\pi(i-1)(j-1)}{N}} + \\ \sum_{j=-1}^{-63} d_{PSS_{126-j}} \cdot e^{\frac{-2\pi(i-1)(N-j)}{N}} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

for $1 \leq i \leq N$ where N is the selected Fourier transform size, which is dependent on the numerology. Based on the maximum number of subcarriers, bandwidth and subcarrier spacing, the ideal Fourier transform size can found to be

4096 for numerologies 0 and 1 and 2048 for numerology 2. The upper-part of the Fourier transform is considered as the resource elements below the carrier frequency and the lower-part of the Fourier transform is considered as the resource elements above the carrier frequency. Similar to the synchronization algorithms defined for LTE [9], the well-defined positioning of the PSS in the NR standard helps for the timing synchronization [17]. The structure of the 5G grid can then be found by knowing that PSS is at OFDM symbol number 0 in the SSB and the locations of SSBs are given according to Table 2.

The index u of the PSS provides $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ which ranges from 0 to 2. This information would be used later on to decode the cell identity. When the correlation is calculated, the sample with the highest correlation value shows the start of the PSS symbol, which provides the timing synchronization.

An example is shown in Fig. 6 for the case of 8 SSBs. $N_{ID}^{(2)} = 0$ yields the highest correlation values with 8 peaks, indicating the start of PSSs in every SSB.

Fig. 6. Example output of correlation for different $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ with 8 SSBs

Extraction of symbols in time domain

Once the timing synchronization is successfully completed, the symbols in time domain can be extracted from the 5G NR signals. This is performed after removing the cyclic prefix of the OFDM modulated signal according to the NR modulation definition for the given configuration [15]. The cyclic prefix lengths are given in Table 3.

μ	$N_{slot}^{subframe \mu}$	N_{symp}^{slot}	Symbol duration $/T_c$	Prefix duration $/T_c$
0	1	14	2048 κ	160 κ for $l = 0, 7$ 144 κ for other values of l
1	2	14	1024 κ	88 κ for $l = 0, 14$ 72 κ for other values of l
2	4	14	512 κ	52 κ for $l = 0, 28$ 36 κ for other values of l

Table 3. Symbol and cyclic prefix durations for different numerologies in T_c (See Eq. (1) and Eq. (2)). l is the OFDM symbol number in a subframe taking values $0, 1, \dots, N_{slot}^{subframe \mu} \cdot N_{symp}^{slot} - 1$ and the extended prefix is applied to the first OFDM symbol of the subframe.

Conversion of symbols in the frequency domain

After obtaining the symbols in time domain, they are converted into the frequency domain in terms of an FFT of length N , which dependent on the selected numerology as mentioned earlier. The upper part of the FFT is considered as the resource element below center frequencies and the lower part of the FFT is considered as the resource element

above the center frequencies. With that, for each slot, the uncorrected resource element $a_{k,l}^{\text{uncorr}}$ (real and imaginary value) of the l^{th} symbol, and the k^{th} subcarrier is obtained.

Channel estimation

When the ideal and the measured PSSs under concern are obtained, the effect of the transmission channel can be estimated. This estimation could be done using linear Minimum Mean Square Error (MMSE) based linear data fitting. The measured PSS is divided by the ideal PSS in the frequency domain complex plane and MMSE-based data fitting is applied to obtain the equalization parameters. Most mathematical modeling and calculation platforms such as MATLAB, Mathematica or Python have the corresponding functions for this purpose.

The phase correction of each 5G resource element is obtained in terms of a first order fit of the decoded PSS sequence [9]:

$$\phi_{\text{corr}}(k, n) = \phi_0 + C_1 \cdot k + C_2 \cdot n \quad (8)$$

Herein, k is the index of the sub-carrier on the frequency axis of the 5G resource grid, whose range depends on the bandwidth of the input signal and Fourier size, and n is the index of the OFDM symbol on the time axis of the 5G grid. Moreover, C_1 and C_2 are the fit coefficients for the sub-carrier and OFDM symbol respectively [9]. The phase and frequency corrections are performed by de-rotating the received OFDM symbol, i.e., multiplying them with $e^{-j2\pi\phi_{\text{corr}}}$ [9]. Note that no frequency dependent amplitude correction has been applied to the measured signal since the channel estimation was considered as flat within the measurement uncertainty.

After all corrections, the resource element $a_{k,l}$ (real and imaginary value) of the l^{th} symbol, and the k^{th} subcarrier is obtained. The frequency correction for the resource element $a_{k,l}$ can be implemented as [9]

$$a_{k,l} = a_{k,l} \cdot c_k \quad (9)$$

An example is given in Fig. 7 for the output of the phase correction.

Fig. 7. Phase correction based on measurement vs. MMSE-based estimation. N_{FFT} is the length of Fourier Transform

The application in a laboratory environment would enable a perfect clock synchronization of the measurement equipment, which typically eliminates the need for frequency correction.

The MMSE-based correction is then extrapolated to cover the entire transmission bandwidth. The correction parameters obtained in this way are applied to the whole resource grid [9].

SSS Decoding

SSS is located on OFDM symbol number 2 in SSB [15]. On the other hand, the physical layer cell identity (N_{ID}^{cell}) is determined using the PSS which provides $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ and SSS which provides $N_{ID}^{(1)}$ [15]. Therefore, the SSS signal must be decoded to find $N_{ID}^{(1)}$.

After successful detecting $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ and achieving timing synchronization, SSS can be detected by applying the following steps to the signal recording, in a similar way to PSS:

- 1) Generation of all SSS sequences based on detected $N_{ID}^{(2)}$
- 2) Mapping to the subcarriers
- 3) Obtaining time domain candidate signals
- 4) Applying correlation to signal record to get $N_{ID}^{(1)}$
- 5) Calculating physical cell ID

The sequence to define the SSS can have 1008 (336×3) possible values [15]. Once $N_{ID}^{(2)}$ is detected, the selection narrows down to 336. Each of these 336 sequences having a length of 127 must be correctly generated. Mapping to the subcarriers and obtaining the time domain candidates are the same as given for PSS. For $N_{FFT} = 4096$, the cyclic prefix for short symbols (CP_{short}) is equal to 288, which makes *SSS Start Sample index* = 8768 samples after PSS. For such a case, a window of 15000 samples shall be taken for correlation calculation.

The index of the candidate signal with the highest correlation value gives the information on $N_{ID}^{(1)}$.

An example is shown in Fig. 8. $N_{ID}^{(1)}$ value of 83 and the sample at 8768 give the highest correlation.

Fig. 8. Example output of correlation for different $N_{ID}^{(1)}$ and the position within the recorded samples

Finally, the N_{ID}^{cell} is determined with the expression [15]

$$N_{ID}^{cell} = 3 \cdot N_{ID}^{(1)} + N_{ID}^{(2)} \quad (10)$$

Obtaining the Cell ID is not absolutely a requirement in the decoding algorithm; however, it constitutes a way to cross check the success of the decoding.

When all these steps are properly achieved, the OFDM symbol carrying the SSS symbol can be extracted and its 4-QAM constellation diagram can be obtained (See Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. When the 5G resource grid is successfully decoded and the OFDM symbol, where SSS lies, is demodulated, the resultant 4-QAM constellation diagram includes various information. The position of SSS symbols is on the real axis (denoted in blue) whereas PBCH signals have imaginary parts as well (denoted in orange), therefore they do not coincide. In the ideal case, the magnitude of all symbols (therefore, of SSS) should be 1, the measured magnitude can be therefore used to calculate the received voltage of SSS.

Estimating the power of the SSS

Finally, the power of the extracted SSS is used for power measurement of the received signals. The power values $P_{k,l}^{(p)}$ (in Watt) of the SSS are simply obtained using the amplitude $a_{k,l}$ (in Volt) of the corresponding resource elements, where the index (p) represents the SSS resource element as [9]:

$$P_{k,l} = \frac{|a_{k,l}|^2}{50\Omega} \quad (11)$$

This equation is based under the assumption of a 50Ω "measuring system" calibrated at the reference impedance of 50Ω . The mismatch caused by the imperfect 50Ω adaption (measured in terms of reflection loss) is further considered in the uncertainty budget. With this, the SSS power of the downlink 5G signal is calculated from the arithmetic mean over all the resource elements that carry the SSS values within the operating bandwidth and within a frame as [9]:

$$P_{fr} = \frac{1}{w} \sum_w P_{k,l} \quad (12)$$

where the summation goes over a total of w SSS resource elements corresponding to the given frame fr .

In a similar way, the standard deviation of these power values can be estimated as follows [9]:

$$\sigma_{fr} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{w} \sum_w (P_{k,l} - P_{fr})^2} \quad (13)$$

This standard deviation is an important number, since it provides an estimate of the "quality" of the measurement and the measurement uncertainty: if the standard deviation is small, it means that all SSS have almost the same power. It suffices to estimate the power based on one radio frame of 10 ms duration. The stability in time of the power measurement can itself be estimated by estimating the standard deviation across many radio frames.

Performing frequency response correction

The absolute calibration of the entire conducted set-up is performed by characterizing the frequency response of the scope amplitude with an input sine wave of known power for the frequency response correction, while constantly observing the output power of sinus generator with another power meter, as given in Fig. 10. Thus, the traceability to the SI units is achieved.

The frequency response of the system is calculated as follows:

$$K(f_{center}) = \frac{P_{ref}(f_{center})}{P_{DSO}(f_{center})} \quad (14)$$

where f_{center} is the frequency of the transmission (i.e., center frequencies given in Table 4), $P_{ref}(f_{center})$ the reference power of a CW signal at the center frequency, and $P_{DSO}(f_{center})$ the power as measured by the oscilloscope of the CW signal at center frequency down converted to the IF frequency.

This factor is applied to the power values of SSS resource elements and the SI traceability is established.

Fig. 10: A sine wave is passed through the proposed set-up for 5G power evaluation and recorded in the oscilloscope as well as measured using a calibrated power meter.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION AND APPLICATION

The precision of the measurement setup and decoding algorithm was experimentally studied in a laboratory environment for both FR1 and FR2 frequency ranges. In order to generate 5G signals, a commercial signal generator (Rohde & Schwarz SMW200A) with 5G option was used. For FR2, the frequency of the signal output of the signal generator was increased using an additional frequency mixer and an additional local oscillator. At the receiving side, the 5G signal generated at the required frequency is passed through a power splitter (VSWR < 1.35, frequency range from DC to 18 GHz for FR1 and to 36 GHz for FR2) and then mixed with RF signal from local oscillator (frequency range from 300 MHz to 26 GHz, local oscillator power of 15 dBm) to obtain IF signal at 45 MHz (On the other side of the power splitter, a power meter is placed in order to monitor the power level.). The IF signal at 45 MHz is then passed through a low pass filter (DC to 70 MHz) to remove the higher harmonics. The output of the low pass filter is then measured using oscilloscope Agilent DSO 90254 (see Fig. 11(a) and (b) for the setups for FR1 and FR2, respectively).

(a) Measurement Setup for FR1

(b) Measurement Setup for FR2

Fig. 11. Experimental setups for 5G SSS power measurement of 5G signal generated by Rohde & Schwarz SMW200A signal generator (a) for FR1 (b) for FR2. The signal generated at the required frequency is passed through a power splitter and then mixed with RF signal from local oscillator to obtain IF signal. This signal is then passed through a low pass filter to remove the higher harmonics. The output of the low pass filter is then measured using oscilloscope Agilent DSO 90254.

We defined five different 5G scenarios to be configured at the 5G generator to perform experimental studies and to test the 5G decoding algorithm along with the analysis of the power evaluation. The scenarios are listed in Table 4.

Scenario Number	Numerology	Frequency Range	Center Frequency /MHz	Channel Bandwidth /MHz	Peak Envelope Power (PEP) /dBm	Power Level /dBm	Number of SSBs
1	0	FR1	800	20	-4	-14.69	4
2	0	FR1	3500	20	-4	-14.78	8
3	1	FR1	800	20	-4	-14.71	4
4	1	FR1	3500	20	-4	-15.04	8
5	3	FR2	25955	50	-4	-11.03	64

Table 4. 5G scenarios for the downlink configured at the 5G signal generator for the evaluation of the proposed oscilloscope-based measurement method.

It is here worth to note that the full traffic case (100% Traffic) was considered for all cases. This means, all REs available for traffic were utilized and filled with random information. This approach helps to assess the robustness of the method and provides the accuracy of the 5G decoding in the worst-case scenario.

After some preliminary checks, it was found out that the setup works fully linear with an input sine wave at power up to -4 dBm. For this reason, the setup was calibrated for the selected center frequencies at this input signal level. The calibration results showed that the path loss from the output of the signal generator to the reading with scope is 14.44 dB, 13.35 dB and 23.94 dB for 800 MHz, 3500 MHz and for 25955 MHz, respectively.

To establish a linear operation, for all scenarios, the selected peak envelope power (PEP) was also selected as -4 dBm. The power level of the 5G signal was then automatically calculated by 5G generator for every scenario (See Table 4). For the measurements, 5G signal generator operated in constant power spectrum density (Constant PSD) mode to keep the RF power of all resource elements constant. Each scenario was measured three times with the testbed and the measurements were analyzed using the software module.

A detailed analysis for SSS resource element (RE) power detection can be made for Scenario 1 as follows:

The theoretical power (meaning the power expected considering the generator settings) of each RE in SSS is calculated given as follows:

$$\text{Power (each RE)}_{\text{dBm}} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} \times \text{Subcarrier Spacing}_{\text{Hz}}) \quad (15)$$

where

$$\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} = \frac{10^{\frac{\text{Set Power}_{\text{dBm}}}{10}}}{\text{Bandwidth}_{\text{Hz}}} \quad (16)$$

The theoretical RE power calculation for Scenario 1 is performed as follows:

For Set Power = -14.69 dBm, Bandwidth = 20 MHz and SCS = 15 kHz (i.e. numerology 0)

$$\text{Power Density}_{\text{mW/Hz}} = \frac{10^{\frac{-14.69}{10}}}{20 \times 10^6} = 1.6981 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mW/Hz} \quad (17)$$

and

$$\text{Power (each RE)}_{\text{dBm}} = 10 \cdot \log_{10}(1.6981 \times 10^{-9} \times 15000) = -45.94 \text{ dBm} \quad (18)$$

This calculation was repeated for all scenarios to obtain the theoretical power of one SSS RE.

On the other hand, the measured SSS RE power is calculated as follows: For the first measurement, the average value of all detected SSS RE powers is calculated. Then, this calculation is repeated for all three measurements and the average of all three measurements is used for the final evaluation. The standard deviation is also calculated similarly. The measurement results are given in Table 5.

Scenario Number	Set Power on Generator /dBm	Theoretical RE Power /dBm	Measured SSS RE Power /dBm	Difference of Theoretical Value and Measured Value /dB	Standard Deviation of SSS RE Powers in a Subframe /dB
1	-14.69	-45.94	-46.00	0.06	0.009
2	-14.78	-46.03	-46.10	0.07	0.014
3	-14.71	-42.95	-43.03	0.08	0.010
4	-15.04	-43.28	-43.29	0.01	0.013
5	-11.03	-37.23	-37.27	0.04	0.018

Table 5. Comparison of theoretical and measured SSS RE Power for all scenarios and the standard deviation of measurements

Sources of Uncertainty and Measurement Uncertainty Budget

There are 5 influencing factors which contribute to the measurement uncertainty according to the guidelines of the JCGM 100:2008 [22].

1. Uncertainty of power reference: In the setup, two different calibrated power meters are used for establishing the SI traceability. In the calibration certificates of the power meters, the uncertainties of these power references are given. Depending on the type and the quality of the power meter, this uncertainty changes. It was found out that the power meter used for FR1 has lower standard uncertainty (0.025 dB) than the one used in FR2 (0.060 dB).

2. Resolution of oscilloscope: The oscilloscope used in the measurement chain has 8-bit resolution. The uncertainty in the voltage amplitude measured by the oscilloscope has a rectangular distribution with distribution factor of 1.73. The amount of the uncertainty is calculated as follows:

$$u_{\text{Scope}}(\text{dB}) = 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2 \times 2^8} \right) = 0.017 \text{ dB} \quad (19)$$

3. Frequency response of the measurement chain: The characterization of the measurement chain using conventional measurement methods such as a VNA or similar would yield the uncertainty contribution from the frequency response of the measurement chain. This effect includes also the broadband characteristics of the chain. In this application, a signal having a bandwidth up to 50 MHz is measured using the chain. The RF mixer and the bandpass filters do not have the same conversion loss throughout the band. This source of uncertainty also considers this factor. The values of 0.03 dB and 0.08 dB for FR1 and FR2 respectively are obtained from the calibration of the chain and the conversion loss characteristics of RF mixer and bandpass filters.

4. Stability of SSS measurements: This factor is obtained by the overestimation of the standard deviation of 50 different SSS measurements.

5. Reproducibility: This source of uncertainty has been investigated and the corresponding contribution of 0.01 dB has been found by repeating measurements for the decoding of the whole resource grid for the exact same configuration.

Number	Source of Uncertainty	Uncertainty /dB	Distribution type	Distribution factor	Standard uncertainty /dB
1	Uncertainty of power reference	0.025 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.060 for 26955 MHz	Normal	2	0.013 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.030 for 26955 MHz
2	Resolution of oscilloscope (8 bits)	0.017	Rectangular	1.73	0.010
3	Frequency response of the measurement chain	0.030 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.080 for 26955 MHz	Rectangular	1.73	0.017 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.046 for 26955 MHz
4	Mismatch uncertainty	Setup reflection loss of -30 dB for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz and of -20 dB for 26955 MHz Generator reflection loss of -20 dB on the whole range	U-Shape	1.41	0.019 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.110 for 26955 MHz
5	Stability of SSS measurements (repeatability)	0.010 for 800 MHz 0.015 for 3500 MHz 0.020 for 26955 MHz	Normal	1	0.010 for 800 MHz 0.015 for 3500 MHz 0.020 for 26955 MHz
6	Reproducibility	0.01 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.03 for 26955 MHz	Normal	1	0.010 for 800 MHz and 3500 MHz 0.03 for 26955 MHz
Total (k=1)					0.034 for 800 MHz 0.036 for 3500 MHz 0.129 for 26955 MHz
Total (k=2)					0.067 for 800 MHz 0.071 for 3500 MHz 0.257 for 26955 MHz

Table 6. Measurement Uncertainty Budget for 5G Measurements (given for all selected center frequencies)

Calibration of Two Commercial 5G Measuring Receivers

The study was extended to calibrate two commercial 5G Measuring Receivers: Deviser EM860 and Narda SRM 3006 (both with 5G options). Both devices operate in sub 6 GHz band, therefore, scenarios 1 to 4 from Table 4 could be applied for the calibration purposes. For the measurements, two measurands are selected:

- 1) The average of the measured maximum SSS power (i.e., "Avg (SSS Max)")
- 2) The average of the measured summation of all SSS powers (i.e., "Avg (SSS Sum)")

For the selected settings, the difference between these measurands is expected to be

- 1) $10 \times \log_{10}4 = 6.02 \text{ dB}$ for scenarios 1 and 3
- 2) $10 \times \log_{10}8 = 9.03 \text{ dB}$ for scenarios 2 and 4

For each of these signals, the following values are reported:

- 1) Set signal power on the 5G signal generator
- 2) "SSS power" value measured with the calibrated METAS setup
- 3) "Avg (SSS Max)" value measured by the DUT
- 4) "Avg (SSS Sum)" value measured by the DUT
- 5) Difference between the measured value "Avg (SSS Max)" and the expected value "SSS power", and its uncertainty.

In a separate table, the deviation of the expected and measured difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum are also reported for each scenario.

The calibration results of Narda SRM 3006 product are given in Table 7 and Table 8.

Scenario Number	Signal Power /dBm	SSS RE Power /dBm	Measured Avg (SSS Max) /dBm	Measured Avg (SSS Sum) /dBm	Difference /dB	Expanded Uncertainty /dB
1	-14.69	-52.45	-52.93	-47.11	0.48	0.067
2	-14.78	-53.42	-53.21	-44.50	-0.21	0.071
3	-14.71	-49.46	-49.80	-43.88	0.34	0.067
4	-15.04	-50.53	-50.43	-41.59	-0.30	0.071

Table 7. Measurement scenarios and results for the calibration of Narda SRM 3006 product

Scenario Number	Expected Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum /dB	Measured Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum /dB	Difference /dB	Expanded Uncertainty /dB
1	6.02	5.82	0.20	0.067
2	9.03	8.71	0.32	0.071
3	6.02	5.92	0.10	0.067
4	9.03	8.84	0.19	0.071

Table 8. Expected and measured difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum values for Narda SRM 3006 Product

The calibration results of Deviser EM860 product are given in Table 9 and Table 10.

Scenario Number	Signal Power /dBm	SSS RE Power /dBm	Measured Avg (SSS Max) /dBm	Measured Avg (SSS Sum) /dBm	Difference /dB	Expanded Uncertainty /dB
1	-14.69	-53.51	-53.83	-47.81	0.32	0.067
2	-14.78	-54.42	-54.63	-45.61	0.21	0.071
3	-14.71	-50.74	-50.76	-44.74	0.02	0.067
4	-15.04	-51.76	-51.82	-42.80	0.06	0.071

Table 9. Measurement scenarios and results for the calibration of Deviser EM860 product

Scenario Number	Expected Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum /dB	Measured Difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum /dB	Difference /dB	Expanded Uncertainty /dB
1	6.02	6.02	0.00	0.067
2	9.03	9.02	0.01	0.071
3	6.02	6.02	0.00	0.067
4	9.03	9.02	0.01	0.071

Table 10. Expected and measured difference between SSS Max and SSS Sum values for Deviser EM860 Product

The results presented here demonstrate that it is feasible to calibrated 5G code-selective commercial receivers, and the calibration tables could be used as correction factors for accredited user of this equipment. The tables shall not be misinterpreted and be used to compare both manufacturer absolute calibration, but more to assess the capability of both devices to detect and measure correctly SSS at different levels compared to the traffic signals. A fair comparison of the devices would have been to perform a calibration of the frequency response in the level recorder and to take it into account for this evaluation.

V. APPLICATION FOR NON-IONIZING RADIATION EXPOSURE MEASUREMENTS

5G technology introduces significant improvements over LTE technology in terms of modularity. Depending on specific requirements, critical parameters such as SCS, bandwidth, frequency ranges can be changed. Moreover, it even allows the co-existence of LTE in the same resource grid. This modularity, however, brings up challenges on the receiver side yielding in more complicated solutions. Consequently, 5G decoding algorithms are more sophisticated compared to LTE.

In the proposed method, the downlink transmission of 5G signals can be decoded in laboratory environments in order to detect the field strength associated with SSS signals. With this reference setup, full traceability can be ensured in the calibration of code-selective commercial 5G measuring receivers.

These code-selective receivers are important to quantify the exposure. As a first step, a stable 5G generator, fed with 5G signals with different configurations (numerology, center frequency, different number of SSBs, etc.), is calibrated by the reference system. Once characterized, the 5G generator can be used to calibrate or validate the measurement capabilities of the commercial measuring receivers. Additionally, this calibration setup can be applied in various fading scenarios, testing the ability of the receiver to accurately assess the amplitude of SSS REs and measure correctly, even in the presence of traffic signals. The verification on commercial 5G measuring receivers for FR2 showed that this calibration method is applicable in order to provide the SI-traceability for this extended range of frequency bands.

VI. CONCLUSION

Proposed 5G decoding method was proven to be efficient and accurate, addressing the challenges posed by the complex signal environment of 5G networks. Through rigorous testing and validation, the method has shown its capability to handle various configurations, ensuring reliability with high precision for both FR1 and FR2 frequencies. As proven here, the flexibility and robustness of the algorithm make it a valuable tool for ensuring the SI traceability of the RF exposure measurements performed using 5G measuring receivers, which is, in turn, important for the public health. With the help of traceable measurements, it is possible to determine the compliance of the base stations to the legal limits of radiation, in a traceable way.

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VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Ericsson, "Ericsson Mobility Report," Ericsson, 2024.
- [2] ICNIRP, "Guidelines for limiting exposure to electromagnetic fields (100 kHz to 300 GHz)," *Health Phys.*, vol. 118, no. 5, pp. 483-524, 2020.
- [3] "Ministère français de la santé et des sports, Secrétariat d'Etat chargée de l'écologie, Secrétariat d'Etat chargé de la prospective et du développement de l'économie numérique. (2009). Fiche 03 – Comparaison des réglementations européennes.," 2009. [Online]. Available: <http://www.radiofrequences.gouv.fr>.
- [4] NCRP, "Recommendations for human exposure to RF electromagnetic fields for Maximum Permissible Exposure limits for field strength and power density for the transmitters operating at frequencies of 300 kHz to 100 GHz.," 1996.
- [5] UDC, *614.898.5 GB 9175 –88. Environmental health standards: Hygienic standard for environmental electromagnetic waves*, 1989.
- [6] BAFU, "814.710, Ordinance relating to Protection from Non-Ionizing Radiation (ONIR)," 1999. [Online]. Available: www.bafu.ch.
- [7] METAS, "Technical Report: Measurement Method for 5G NR Base Stations up to 6 GHz," 2020.
- [8] *5G; NR; Physical layer procedures for control (3GPP TS 38.213 version 17.4.0; Release 17)*, 2023.
- [9] S. S. Dash, F. Pythoud, P. Leuchtman and J. Leuthold, "Method for traceable measurement of LTE signals," *Metrologia*, vol. 55, no. 2, 2018.
- [10] A. Fellan and H. D. Schotten, "Overview of the Evaluation Methods for the Maximum EMF Exposure in 5G Networks," in *IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*, Thessaloniki, Greece, 2022.
- [11] L. -M. Schilling, C. Bornkessel and M. A. Hein, "Analysis of Instantaneous and Maximal RF Exposure in 4G/5G Networks With Dynamic Spectrum Sharing," in *16th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, Madrid, Spain, 2022.
- [12] C. Bornkessel, T. Kopacz, A. -M. Schiffahrt, D. Heberling and M. A. Hein, "Determination of Instantaneous and Maximal Human Exposure to 5G Massive-MIMO Base Stations," in *15th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, Dusseldorf, Germany, 2021.
- [13] "LTE; Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA); Physical channels and modulation (3GPP TS 36.214 version 9.2.0; Release 9)," 2020.
- [14] *5G; NR; Base station (BS) radio transmission and reception (3GPP TS 38.104 version 17.8.0; Release 17)*, 2023.
- [15] *5G; NR; Physical channels and modulation (3GPP TS 38.211 version 17.4.0; Release 17)*, 2023.

- 1
2
3 [16] J. Proakis and M. Salehi, Digital Communications, 5 ed., McGraw-Hill, 2008.
4
5 [17] T. Yingming, Z. Guodong, D. Grieco and F. Ozluturk, "Cell search in 3GPP long term evolution systems,"
6 *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 23-29, 2007.
7
8 [18] K. Manolakis, D. M. Gutierrez Estevez, V. Jungnickel, W. Xu and C. Drewes, "A Closed Concept for
9 Synchronization and Cell Search in 3GPP LTE Systems," in *Wireless Communications and Networking
10 Conference*, 2009.
11
12 [19] M. Morelli and M. Moretti, "A Robust Maximum Likelihood Scheme for PSS Detection and Integer Frequency
13 Offset Recovery in LTE Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1353-
14 1363, 2016.
15
16 [20] M. Hua, M. Wang, K. W. Yang and K. J. Zou, "Analysis of the Frequency Offset Effect on Zadoff-Chu
17 Sequence Timing Performance," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 62, no. 11, pp. 4024-4039, 2014.
18
19 [21] S. Sesia, I. Toufik and M. Baker, LTE, The UMTS Long Term Evolution: From Theory to Practice, Wiley
20 Publishing, 2009, p. 648.
21
22 [22] *JCGM 100:2008. Evaluation of measurement data — Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement*,
23 2008.
24
25
26
27
28
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30
31
32
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